

GALECUMB EXTRACTS AS TERMITE REPELLENT

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GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent

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Abstract

Termites cause structural damage to residential and commercial buildings. Chemical repellents are commonly used to address this issue, but concerns have been raised regarding their long-term effects on health and the environment. Customers have complained with the repellents' odor and the discoloration on wood surfaces. Alternative solutions may have been explored in previous studies, limited research has been done on a combination of garlic, lemon, and cucumber extracts (GaLeCumb). To address this, the study explored the effectiveness and acceptability of GaLeCumb as an alternative organic repellent in terms of repelling termites, duration, odor, and discoloration, compared to the commercial product. The gathering of numerical data through a quantitative method began after steam distillation and formulation of three repellents were done. Following this was a 14-day observation where 4 single-choice tests were performed to evaluate termite repellency. It was revealed that Formulation 2 had the best formulation. Fifteen woodworking experts were purposely sampled as respondents of the study. In the analysis of results, it was revealed that the developed repellent was effective in repelling a high percentage of termites all throughout 24 hours. In addition, data showed that there is a significant difference between the commercially done product ($SD = 3.28$) and the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent ($SD = 1.22$). Mean scores showed that GaLeCumb Termite Repellent was “very much acceptable” in terms of both odor ($M = 3.98$) and discoloration ($M = 3.7$). These findings contribute valuable insights for future researchers, addressing gaps and limitations in the field of termite repellent.

Keywords: *termite repellent, garlic, lemon, cucumber, organic*

Introduction

The tropical environment and high humidity make the Philippines an ideal breeding environment for termites. This insect feeds on decaying plant materials including wood, which is the biggest cause of home damage in the Philippines, with 205,000 Pesos estimated average cost of damage (Sare, 2021). While various chemical-based termite control methods are available in the market, the potential health hazards have led researchers to explore alternative, natural solutions for termite control. One potential natural alternative is the use of plant extracts due to their potential effectiveness as repellents. Hence, this study focuses on investigating the effectiveness of garlic, lemon, and cucumber extracts as termite repellents.

Prolonged and constant human exposure to chemical repellent can lead to chronic illnesses such as cancer and neurological diseases. The current solution of using chemical repellents has numerous weaknesses, including potential adverse effects on human health, toxic waste produced as a result of using these products, strong odor, and discoloration that occurs after application. Furthermore, some organic ingredients in repellents tend to spoil quickly. Consequently, there is a growing interest in exploring natural alternatives that pose minimal risks. Despite the existence of several studies about chemical-based termite repellents, the body of research on natural alternatives, specifically, garlic (*Allium sativum*), lemon (*Citrus limon*), and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) extracts as a combination, remains limited. Therefore, there is a significant gap in the existing literature that this study seeks to address, presenting an opportunity to explore the potential of these extracts as termite repellents.

The proposed solution by the researchers is to switch to using organic repellents which can address the issues of toxic waste disposal, provide a combination of different organic ingredients as repellents for better efficacy, offer a natural scent that is more pleasant, prevent any alteration of wood appearance, and ensure that the organic ingredients will not spoil easily. Hence, garlic, lemon, and cucumber are the three main ingredients chosen by the researchers because of their repelling properties. Garlic, for example, as mentioned in the paper “Fact Sheet *Allium Sativum* (Garlic)” by United States Environmental Protection Agency [EPA] (1992) that summarizes the information in the Registration Eligibility Document, or RED, for *Allium Sativum*. From 1983 to 1991, there were a total of 4 EPA registered pesticides that use garlic as an active ingredient, stating that the repellents are unlikely to cause unreasonable negative effects on people or the environment.

Based on the conducted studies, the cost-effective use of natural ingredients as pest repellents. Garlic and lemon peels were found to be affordable and efficient in managing stored grain pests and repelling insects, respectively (Onu et al., 2015; Mendoza, 2021). While another study investigated the effectiveness of a cucumber and baking soda solution as a cockroach repellent, highlighting the affordability of cucumber as a key ingredient (Castro et al., 2024). These studies suggest the potential of using natural ingredients as a practical and budget-friendly approach to pest control. Hence, lemon peel, cucumber, and garlic were chosen for their repellent properties and accessibility. Lemon peel contains limonene and citral, which are known to repel insects including termites. Cucumber has a high-water content which can help to keep the wood hydrated and less attractive to termites. Garlic contains sulfur compounds that are also effective at repelling termites. Additionally, all three ingredients are natural and non-toxic, making them a safe option for termite control.

The study aligns with 17 Sustainable Development Goals by the United Nations (2025) wherein SD Goals 9 and 15 by exploring natural alternatives to chemical-based termite repellents, and in accordance with Section 6 (I. 2) of the Presidential Decree No. 1144 also known as Creating the Fertilizer and Pesticide Authority and Abolishing the Fertilizer Industry Authority. The main objective of this research is to evaluate the effectiveness of GaLeCumb extracts as a termite repellent, specifically, to determine the best formulation of GaLeCumb repellent and measure their acceptability, effectiveness, and significant difference between a commercially done product. By conducting comprehensive experiments and field trials, the study intends to provide valuable insights into the potential use of GaLeCumb extracts as an alternative to existing termite repellents.

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to the development of natural methods for termite control. If the research findings confirm the effectiveness of garlic, lemon, and cucumber extracts as termite repellents, it could have various implications. First, it would provide homeowners and property owners with a safer and more sustainable alternative to chemical-based termite control methods. Then, this study could encourage the utilization of locally available plants, promoting their economic value and potentially benefit local communities. The study will also serve as a guide for other researchers and answers for the lack of information on the topic.

Moreover, the investigation of researchers about GaLeCumb extracts as termite repellents is an essential area of research that will bridge the gap in existing knowledge and explore the combined effects of garlic, lemon, and cucumber extracts as alternative to existing termite repellents.

Research Questions

This study seeks to develop, validate and test the effectiveness of GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. This study sought to determine the effectiveness in terms of:
 - 1.1. repelling termites; and
 - 1.2. duration of repellency?
2. Is there any significant difference between the GaLeCumb Repellent and the commercially done product in the above-mentioned variables?
3. This study sought to determine the acceptability in terms of:
 - 3.1. odor; and
 - 3.2. discoloration?

Literature Review

Repelling Termites

Studies discuss several preventive measures, such as keeping the surroundings clean and removing any sources of moisture. It provides a comprehensive analysis of the different methods used for termite control, with a specific focus on efficacy testing requirements. It highlights the need for effective methods of repelling these termites, given their destructive nature and economic impact. The studies focus on the use of organic pesticides as a safer alternative to conventional repellents. Also, they explore the effectiveness of these natural agents in deterring termite infestations, highlighting their potential in repelling termites without posing harm to the environment or human health. (Matt, 2023; Oi et al., 2022; Williamson, 2023; Omar, 2018)

To determine the effectiveness of the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent in repelling termites and assess the significant difference in commercially done product, the study will follow a scientific process adapted by the researchers. The termite trap method was utilized for a project in FRIM, Kepong, Selangor, Malaysia. Cardboards were cut into 10 cm lengths and organized in three rows before being thoroughly rinsed with distilled water and positioned back in the basin. The termite trap was placed at a tree bark location, and all collected termites were preserved alive. (Zawawi et al., 2021). It is the best and ethical method since another study examines the termiticidal efficacy of citrus peel extracts against termites, specifically *Macrotermes bellicosus*. The study uses the method of shovel collection for termites, where researchers dig up the termite mound to gather specimens for testing the effect of citrus peel extracts on these termites (Edwin, 2017). Next, Carolina's Care Guide emphasizes the importance of providing proper housing for termites to ensure their health and well-being. The guide recommends creating a suitable environment with moisture and food sources to attract termites, such as wood or cellulose materials. It also advises on the importance of monitoring the termite population and controlling infestations to prevent damage to structures. Lastly, current researchers adapted also the Standard Test Method for Laboratory Evaluation of Wood for Resistance to Subterranean Termites which is an international standard that was developed in accordance with internationally recognized principles on standardization established in the Decision on Principles for the Development of International Standards, Guides and Recommendations, issued by the World Trade Organization Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) Committee, wherein the paper specified procedures such as conditioning the termite and the test blocks for the repellent and conducting the two choice test method in determining its effectiveness. The Standard Test Method for Laboratory Evaluation of Wood for Resistance to Subterranean Termites uses the two-choice test method to effectively evaluate the application of repellent in wood. This method involves presenting termites with two choices, one treated with the repellent and one untreated, to determine their preference and

effectiveness of the repellent. By utilizing this method, researchers can assess the ability of wood to resist termites and identify the most effective repellents for termite control.

Moreover, the best method for extracting key ingredients for repellent production is through steam distillation, which efficiently captures and concentrates the active compounds in lemongrass. Another study has found a scientific approach to extract the properties of raw ingredients using the steam distillation method. This method is highlighted as the best method of extraction due to its ability to efficiently capture and concentrate the active compounds, maximizing the repellent properties of the final product. (Gumban, 2013; Peñalver, 2023)

Then in order to improve and test the effectiveness of the GaLeCumb termite repellent, the pest control expert advises changing the method to a single-choice method instead of the two-choice test method. In relation to these, to adhere to the ethical standards of the research project, the expert advises diluting the formulation of the termite repellent with 70% solvent of hydrosol or distillate of the ingredients, changing the size of the containers, and elevating the sand in the single-choice method. While, 70% water for dilution of the commercial product. (Panday, 2024).

Duration of Repellency

Then, another study highlights that the shelf life of liquid organic formulations is relatively short and prone to spoilage. This indicates that these products have a limited duration before they become expired or ineffective, making it important for consumers to use them promptly. The research underscores the importance of proper storage and handling of liquid organic formulations to ensure their efficacy and safety for use (Usha & Rameeza, 2016). In contrast, the researches focused on the duration of the termiticides, evaluating how effective they were in preventing termite infestation over time. This highlights the importance of considering environmental factors when determining the duration of repellency of termiticide protection and emphasizes the need for regular monitoring and reapplication to maintain effective termite control. By focusing on the duration of repellency, the study provides valuable insights into the long-lasting protective properties and highlighted that certain termiticides displayed prolonged repellent properties even after exposure, showcasing their potential for long-term termite control in inundated environments. (Acda, 2017; Parvez et al., 2023; Acapulco, 2015; Sapkota, 2018)

To determine the duration of the repellency, researchers will use the observation adapted from different study. Specifically, one conducted a study on the development and characterization of a mosquito repellent fabric using a mixture of peppermint and garlic finishes on knitted fabric. The researchers focused on examining the effectiveness of the organic repellent by conducting observations to determine the duration of mosquito repellency. Through their study, they were able to demonstrate the potential of using natural ingredients such as peppermint and garlic to create fabric that effectively repels mosquitoes, highlighting the importance of observation in evaluating the longevity of the repellent properties (Parvez et al., 2023).

Odor

Going to another variable, the extract's phytochemical constituents and strong odor are both likely to play a role in its insecticidal activity. The research focuses on understanding how insects respond to different odors and their potential effects on their foraging patterns. These studies provide valuable insights into the importance of odors in guiding insect behavior and highlight the significance of understanding the interplay between attraction and repellency. The studies emphasize the potential of using natural plant extracts as repellents, particularly due to their distinctive odors. (Belmi et al., 2014; Verschut et al., 2019; Miranda et al., 2023; Gitahi, 2021). However, the impact of smelly chemical compounds on the environment is a concern due to their long-lasting effects as they examined it. These odors can disrupt ecosystems, contaminate air and water sources, and pose a threat to human and wildlife well-being. Implementing sustainable and eco-friendly alternatives is crucial to minimize the negative effects of chemical compounds on the environment (Salman & Radhi, 2022).

Discoloration

On the other hand, a study emphasizes the necessity of applying moth repellent finishing to woolen textiles and woods to prevent damage from moth larvae, while also noting the potential issue of discoloration that may occur as a result of the application process (Medha et al., 2021). Consequently, one of the key challenges faced in this research is the discoloration of the repellent when applied to wood or other objects/materials. Researchers are working to improve the formulation of the repellent to prevent discoloration while maintaining its effectiveness. It underscores also that natural repellents have no adverse impact on wood properties, particularly discoloration, highlighting their potential as effective and environmentally friendly termite control methods. These studies highlight the importance of utilizing natural repellents as a safe and effective means of pest control without compromising the aesthetic of the wood material (Acda, 2013; Liskova et al., 2022; Bacani et al., 2020; Aras et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the effectiveness of natural agents in repelling termites is investigated in a study. The study highlights the potential of organic pesticides as a safer alternative to conventional repellent that can deter termite infestations without posing harm to the environment or human health. This research emphasizes the significance of utilizing natural methods for termite control, and it connects with above mentioned studies that explores the effectiveness of natural substances in repelling termites. Overall, the study enlightens the potential of organic approaches for termite management (Omar, 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized developmental and experimental research design as defined by Ibrahim (2016), developmental research design is a methodical process of planning, creating, assessing, and production that conceptualizes innovation and improvement to give a specific solution to a problem. The designs were essential to the study because it involved observation and description of the developed product. The researcher can develop and validate a new termite control method that is effective and safe.

Participants

Supported by the developmental research design, this study used non-probability sampling specifically purposive sampling in determining its participants. Fifteen (15) experts consist of woodworkers were selected to evaluate GaLeCumb Termite Repellent in terms of its odor and discoloration.

Their involvement in the study yielded comprehensive comments and analysis and suggestions relevant to the development of the GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent.

Procedure

The study involved a Gantt chart as a guide for the research process. The main topic was defined, and the research question was presented. In-depth readings of related literature were conducted, and a research plan was created. A questionnaire checklist was made by the researchers, and a certificate of content validation and a permit were obtained. The scientific process involved extraction via steam distillation is then conducted in Morong National High School's laboratory to extract the essential oils from the chopped garlic, lemon peels, and cucumber slices. Steam is passed through the plant material, causing the essential oils to vaporize and separate from the water. The essential oils were extracted using steam distillation, preserving their potency. The resulting mixture is then collected and allowed to cool, enabling the separation of the essential oils from the water using a separatory funnel. Prior to creating the final repellent product, three different formulations will be created for the experiment and each one will be tested individually on wood surfaces to identify the most effective formula of the product. For the first formulation the ratio of the organic mixture of 3 whole lemon, 3 whole cucumber and ¼ kilo of Garlic (30 ml extract), second formulation with combining 10% concentration per ingredient, and lastly with a ratio of 2:2:2 of ingredients. The mixture was then combined to create the GaLeCumb Repellent formulation. To make it diluted, the best formulation had 70% solvent which is hydrosol or distillate extracts of the ingredients, while the commercially done product had 70% water.

The termites were collected in a real-life setting in the Woodland of Rodriguez St. Morong, Rizal. The researchers built a termite trap made of plastic container measuring (20 cm length, 10 cm height) and drilling holes measuring (7 cm height x 4 cm width) at the bottom of it as an open tunnel and putting up fresh wood inside. It will be put up in a visible termite mound found by the researchers to ethically collect the termites without harming its natural habitat. The researchers will brush the termites in a controlled environment, such as an enclosed container measuring (5.1 inches diameter and 2.79 inches height) with suitable conditions for their survival. Then, placing wood/plant materials and damp tissue in each layer of the termite housing. It will also seal and keep in a cool and dry place to maintain the necessary moisture for the termites. Additional ventilation holes will also be added to prevent excess moisture buildup. Also, the termites are monitored to ensure their health and activity levels before conducting experiments or applying repellents. The termites should be conditioned at least 24 hours before experimentation.

An experiment adapted from the Standard Test Method for Laboratory Evaluation of Wood for Resistance to Subterranean Termites and modified using single-choice test. The single-choice test method requires a container measuring 8x2'3x5 inches. The container contains damp sand which is screened and washed using distilled water. The water content will be based on the species of termites that will be gathered in the study. For the test blocks, the researchers use pine wood specifically Palochina measuring (2 inches length, 1 inch width, and 0.5 inch height) with no visible damage then, condition and check the test blocks' mass prior for termite exposure. The experiment will have 3 trials: T1, T2, T3, and brand X (T4). The repellent is tested individually per container. Three treated with the natural repellent product and the other with the commercially available termite repellent. These treated wood blocks are then placed and labeled in a container then outgas for 24 hours. There are 80 sample population of termites consisting of 10 soldiers and 10 workers to observe their behavior and assess the effectiveness in repelling termites. The enclosed container with the treated wooden blocks and termites is monitored over a 2-weeks period of time to observe the termites' reactions and behaviors towards the natural repellent product compared to the commercially available product. The researchers carefully note any differences in termite activity, such as avoidance of the treated wood or changes in movement patterns and evaluating the test blocks visual appearance. The termites used in the study should not be released again after the experiment in order to prevent additional damage and infestation. According to Carolina Care Guide for Termites, it has to be frozen for a week in a sealable container before being disposed of with ordinary solid waste container.

Moreover, the finished product is an oil based termite repellent. After that, the questionnaire checklist was answered by respondents to evaluate the acceptability of the GaLeCumb Repellent. Subsequently, the researcher collected and tallied data along with the insights, which were all crucial to the completeness of the study.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations in research are critical to guarantee the welfare, rights, and veracity of the involved people. Thus, this study ensured the informed consent as it was vital to briefly explain the purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits of the study among them. Also, the privacy and confidentiality of the participants especially their personal information were well-thought-out to keep their identities and access to sensitive information were delimited.

On the other hand, the researcher ensured equity and fairness to avoid impartialities, biases and prejudices. This feat guaranteed the objectivity and elimination of conflict of interest which may affect the result of the study.

For the experiment, the researchers dilute the repellent and make a few changes to the procedure to ensure that no termites will be harmed during the experiment.

Results and Discussion

The Effectiveness of GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of Repelling Termites and Duration of Repellency

Table 1. *Computed Mean and Standard Deviation of the Effectiveness of GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of Repelling Termites*

Days	GaLeCumb Termite Repellent		Commercially done product	
	Mean repellence \pm SD	VI	Mean repellence \pm SD	VI
1	16 \pm 2.16	Fairly repellent	7 \pm 4.32	Moderately repellent
2	15 \pm 4.03	Fairly repellent	10 \pm 4.55	Fairly repellent
3	15 \pm 3.30	Fairly repellent	13 \pm 3.46	Average repellency
4	15 \pm 3.51	Fairly repellent	8 \pm 4.97	Fairly repellent
5	17 \pm 1.71	Very repellent	11 \pm 4.69	Moderately repellent
6	17 \pm 4.51	Very repellent	15 \pm 3.57	Average repellency
7	16 \pm 2.08	Fairly repellent	17 \pm 2.83	Fairly repellent
8	15 \pm 3.42	Fairly repellent	12 \pm 4.76	Very repellent
9	15 \pm 3.77	Fairly repellent	14 \pm 4.24	Average repellency
10	18 \pm 2.65	Very repellent	16 \pm 4.08	Fairly repellent
11	14 \pm 2.99	Fairly repellent	9 \pm 4.40	Fairly repellent
12	17 \pm 3.32	Fairly repellent	7 \pm 3.16	Average repellency
13	15 \pm 3.59	Fairly repellent	13 \pm 5.48	Moderately repellent
14	14 \pm 2.36	Fairly repellent		Fairly repellent

The table shows that the day 5, 6, and 10 got the verbal interpretation “very repellent”, having day 10 with the highest mean repellence which is 18. While the rest got “fairly repellent” which ranges from 14 to 16. As observed at the time of exposure, there is an inconsistency in the movement of termites or the repellent effect, which indicates that the effect of the repellent is not time- dependent. Overall, the data suggests that the treatment was effective in repelling a high percentage of termites. Meanwhile, the verbal interpretation for commercially done product lies at “fairly repellent” to “very repellent”.

The results further implied that GaLeCumb Termite Repellent is effective at repelling termites, with a strong repellent effect observed as early as day 1 and lasting through day 14. Although the repellent effect wasn’t constantly increasing over time, it did achieve a very repellent state comparable to commercially available products.

The said implication is similar to Omar (2018) which investigates the efficacy of natural agents in repelling termites. The study focuses on the use of organic pesticides as a safer alternative to conventional repellent. Both study explores the effectiveness of these natural agents in deterring termite infestations, highlighting their potential in repelling termites without posing harm to the environment or human health.

Table 2. *Computed Mean of the Effectiveness of GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of Duration of repellency*

Duration	Mean (hours)	Verbal Interpretation
GaLeCumb Termite Repellent	24	Very Effective
Commercially Done Product	24	Very Effective

The table reveals the mean duration, in hours, of the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent’s effectiveness over a 14-day period. The average of it is 24 with verbal interpretation of “very effective”. It is also the same with the mean and verbal interpretation for commercially done product. Overall, the two repellent was effective in repelling termites for 24 hours each day over a 2-weeks period. This suggests that the repellent may be effective for a full day of the entire observation.

The results further implied that the results from Table 2 are highly effective, indicating that both GaLeCumb Termite Repellent and the commercial product achieved a “very effective” repellent duration of 24 hours per day for the entire 14-day observation period. This suggests that GaLeCumb Termite Repellent may provide consistent, long-lasting protection against termites throughout a day,

potentially for up to two weeks even if it is made from organic ingredients, which is comparable to the performance of existing commercial repellents.

The said implication is similar to Acapulco (2015) that studied the effectiveness of Lanzones peelings' extract as a termite repellent and found that it was highly effective in repelling termites. Acapulco et al.'s study emphasizes the use of organic ingredients with long-lasting properties in repelling insects. These two research demonstrates the potential for natural repellents to effectively repel termites for a long time.

The Significant Difference between GaLeCumb Termite Repellent and Commercially done product in the above-mentioned variables

Table 3. *Computed Independent T-test of the Significance Difference between GaLeCumb Termite Repellent and Commercially done product in the above-mentioned variables*

	Group	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig.	H _o	VI
Repelling Termites	GaLeCumb Termite Repellent	15.64	1.22	4.05	26	0.00049	R	S
	Commercially done product	11.86	3.28					
Duration of repellency	GaLeCumb Termite Repellent	24	0	0	26	1	A	NS
	Commercially done product	24	0					

The table shows that the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent ($M = 15.64$, $SD = 1.22$) compared to the Chemical Termite Repellent, the commercially done product ($M = 11.86$, $SD = 3.28$) demonstrated significant difference in terms of repelling termites, $t(26) = 4.05$, $p = 0.000409$. The t-value is 4.05119. The p-value is 0.000409. The result is significant at $p < .05$. Because of this, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent and the commercially done product in terms of repelling termites is rejected. However, the table also reveals that the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent ($M = 24$, $SD = 0$) compared to the Chemical Termite Repellent, the commercially done product ($M = 24$, $SD = 0$) showed no significant difference in terms of duration of repellency, $t(26) = 0$, $p = 1$. The result is not significant at $p > .05$. Because of this, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent and the commercially done product in terms of duration of repellency is accepted.

The results further implied that the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent may be more effective at repelling termites compared to the commercially available product, based on the statistically significant difference in their means. However, there seems to be no significant difference between the two products in terms of how long the repellent effect lasts.

The said implication is similar to Acadmin (2023) which stated that although chemical companies may try to convince you otherwise, natural bug repellent is proven to be more effective than chemical alternatives. Chemical repellents mask certain odors and signals that insects seek out, while natural repellents create surfaces that are unappealing to bugs. Also, Affandi et al. (2018) conducted a study to determine the effectiveness of natural agents as organic pesticides compared to traditional chemical repellents for termite control. Their findings revealed that both natural and chemical repellents showed similar durations, indicating that the effectiveness of the natural agents was comparable to that of the chemical pesticides.

Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed GaLeCumb Termite Repellent in terms of Odor and Discoloration

Table 4 below shows the evaluation of the experts on the developed GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of odor. It could be noted that all of the indicators under this factor were evaluated as very much acceptable and it attained an overall mean score of 3.98.

As revealed in the table, the indicator, "The GaLeCumb Termite Repellent does not have a strong smell.", "The smell of the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent is not irritating when inhaled.", "It can only smell the repellent if the person gets very close to the wood." attaining a mean of 4.

It can be implied that the product is not harmful and shows improvement of termite repellents odor that is a very important feature of termite control methods. It is very important to consider these qualities to improve livelihood. Also, this result suggest that the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent may be a good option for those who are concerned about the odor of chemical termite repellents.

The said implication is similar to Potter (2018) which explains that homeowners can effectively control termites using repellents made from natural ingredients that are non-toxic and do not have a strong odor. These natural repellents are safe to use around the home and are not offensive to the olfactory senses, making them a practical and environmentally friendly option for termite control.

Table 4. *Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of Odor*

	Factor 1: Odor	Mean	VI
1.	The GaLeCumb Termite Repellent does not have a strong smell.	4	VMA
2.	GaLeCumb Termite Repellent smell does not last long.	3.93	VMA
3.	The smell of GaLeCumb Termite Repellent is not irritating when inhaled.	4	VMA
4.	It can only smell repellent if the person gets very close to the treated wood.	4	VMA
Overall		3.98	VMA

On the other hand, table 5 below shows the evaluation of the experts on the developed GaLeCumb Termite Repellent in terms of Discoloration. It could be distinguished that all of the indicators under this factor were also evaluated as very much acceptable and attained an overall mean score of 3.7.

Table 5. *Evaluation of the Experts on the GaLeCumb Extracts as Termite Repellent in terms of Discoloration*

	Factor 2: Discoloration	Mean	VI
1.	The wood treated with the GaLeCumb Repellent does not show signs of discoloration after application.	3.6	VMA
2.	GaLeCumb Termite Repellent does not fade the color of the wood when applied.	3.93	VMA
3.	The repellent does not stain the wood surface.	3.6	VMA
4.	It preserves the natural color of the wood when applied.	3.67	VMA
		3.7	VMA

The indicator, “GaLeCumb Termite Repellent does not fade the color of the wood when applied.” attained the highest with mean score of 3.93. It can be implied that it doesn’t affect the overall aesthetic appeal of the wood after the application of the product.

The implication of these results suggests that the GaLeCumb Termite Repellent, developed with natural ingredients, is well-received and considered very much acceptable, particularly for not altering the original color of treated wood. This indicates that the product’s performance is satisfactory and meets the expectations of users, potentially making it a viable option for homeowners looking for effective termite control solutions that do not compromise the aesthetic of their wooden structures. It can also be implied that it is important to preserve the quality of the product without compromising its effectiveness.

The said implication is similar to Liskova et al.’s (2022) study on the use of lavender oil as an eco-friendly alternative to protect wood against termites highlights the importance of natural repellents that do not negatively impact wood properties, including discoloration. The research emphasizes that natural solutions can effectively repel termites while preserving the integrity and aesthetics of the wood.

Conclusions

With respect to the results, it was concluded that the Galecumb termite repellent was found to be highly effective in terms of repelling termites and duration, was found to have a significant difference with the commercially done product in repelling termites but no significant difference in duration of repellency, and was perceived very much acceptable in terms of odor and discoloration.

With respect to the conclusion, it was recommended to extend the observation period to more than 14 days, test the product’s repellency on other crawling insects for maximum utilization, experiment with different ingredients and formulations when conducting parallel studies, explore alternative extraction techniques for time efficiency, survey outside woodworking and pest control communities, and dilute the repellent using the same parameters.

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